

COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS OF THE OFFLINE AND ONLINE APPROACHES TO DEVELOPMENT OF PEDAGOGICAL STRATEGIES IN TRAINING ENGLISH TEACHERS

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Abstract

The article is devoted to comparative analysis of efficacy of offline and online approaches to development of students' pedagogical strategies. The peculiarities of pedagogical discourse are described, especially, its interactional aspect. Analysis of the practice of English teachers training shows that both offline and online formats of education are applied. To understand what is more effective for mastering pedagogical strategies the main peculiarities of offline and online teaching are analysed and compared. Besides the survey of the students attitude to offline and online approaches to development of pedagogical strategies is described.

Keywords: *offline, online, EL teachers, pedagogical discourse, pedagogical strategies, comparative analysis, survey.*

Introduction

The processes of globalization and integration and extending cyber space in the modern world impact on the rethinking the requirements to the Modern Languages Teacher's Training. In Uzbekistan context the graduates of the Foreign languages faculties should achieve C1 level of language proficiency to organize the pedagogical activity and pedagogical interaction. The modern language specialists have real opportunities to participate in international projects, webinars and online conferences. That is why the role of online approach for mastering pedagogical discourse has been still great. From theoretical and applied points of view the efficacy of the online approach to teaching pedagogical discourse there is no doubt among the local educators (See: Makhkamova, 2019; Makhkamova & Safarova, 2022). However, there have been some issues which need to be discussed in the framework of teaching pedagogical discourse. One of the issue is related to efficacy of development of pedagogical strategies.

Nowadays the offline and online, as well as blended learning forms of education are implemented in the practice of FL teachers training. Besides traditional approach to offline teaching the electronic or online materials are widely used by teachers to intensify professionally-oriented educational process. This article discusses what among them is more successful for mastering students' pedagogical strategies in Tashkent State Pedagogical University (TSPU) named after Nizami located in Uzbekistan. undoubtedly

Research methods.

Teaching pedagogical discourse for conducting the oral and written professional communication is the one of the objectives of the national curriculum in training teachers of a foreign language at the pedagogical university. According to T.A. Dijk and G.T. Makhkamova, discourse is a communicative event organized by communicants. Exactly, the message, or speech, or any verbal or nonverbal action are considered as a discourse. It is not a new idea that while pedagogical discourse production the teacher use nonverbal means of communication as body language signals, as well as paralinguistic means to perform the affective, semantic and illocutive aspects of pedagogical interaction. Many of scholars deal with the discourse as process and product under the linguistic, extralinguistic, pragmatic, and

cognitive factors [Dijk, 1997; Bernstein, 1990; Martin & Rose, 2013; Rose, 2014; Makhkamova, 2019].

Thus, communication in a class is universal pedagogical discourse where participants play a certain role and fulfill various functions. It is known that education concerns to the socialization process. By the help of pedagogical discourse, the students obtain knowledge and master abilities for further socialization and self-realization. The priority goal of the pedagogical discourse in a foreign language education is socialization, that proposes cultivating cultural values and conventional norms of communicative behavior, imparting the knowledge and development of skills are necessary for communication in the target language. The priority aspect of pedagogical discourse is expressed by interactional strategies while educational process. In particular, pedagogical discourse is represented with the help of different strategies: explanation, assessment, praise, approval and disapproval, etc. [Walsh, 2006; Makhkamova, 2019]. As authors of the article claim in their previous publications, "The secrets of pedagogical experience-exchanging can be realized in different types of interaction in the classroom and ways of solving major educational problems" [Makhkamova & Safarova, 2019: 195]. Any type of pedagogical discourse includes multilevel components related to language system and genre-stylistic peculiarities [Rose, 2014] and functional aspect [Makhkamova, 2019], so, it is difficult task for organizing rational development of students' pedagogical strategies at higher schools. Even more so offline or online approaches applied in higher schools. That is why the information about offline and online teaching specificity and rationality are needed for discussion.

The main peculiarities of offline and online teaching.

While FL teachers training the pedagogical discourse is an important part of offline and online approaches to cultivating. Regarding the mastery of pedagogical discourse, the teachers should realise the features of these two types of education and rationales in obtaining certain knowledge and skills to be a good teacher in a foreign language classes. In traditional offline and diverse environments, teaching usually occurs face-to-face between teachers and students, with real-time communication. It includes verbal and non-verbal

communication, class discussions and interactive sessions. Offline teaching discussion can help students develop a sense of community by providing rapid feedback, personal communication, and social interaction. Teachers can employ various instructional techniques, such as questioning, modeling, and providing real-world examples, to facilitate meaningful discussions and promote active learning. In contrast, online teaching pedagogical discourse occurs in virtual environments and relies on digital communication tools. Nowadays this format presents unique challenges and opportunities for learning a language of specialty. Online pedagogical discourse often takes the form both written and spoken communication, such as discussion forums, chat rooms, or email exchanges [Swan, 2004]. In spite

of the lack of face-to-face communication in online format of education, online platforms offer the advantage of asynchronous communication, allowing students to participate whenever they want. Additionally, online communication can create interactive writing, as well as an inclusive learning environment that allows students who are reluctant to talk face to face to participate in the discussion. That's why in online environments, teachers need to provide clear guidelines, facilitate discussions, and ensure active participation through structured activities [Salmon, 2011]. As it was shown above many factors could come into play when comparing courses in offline and online instructions. The results of comparative analysis are summarized in the Table 1.

Table 1.

The advantages and disadvantages of offline and online approaches.

Advantages and disadvantages	Offline	Online
Advantages	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - live communication with the teacher and other students; - favourable emotional phone to motivate students; - listening the teaching material; - quick feed-back and monitor of the students' progress; - possibility to identify students learning style at once; - developing interpersonal interactive skills in classes. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • - flexible schedule for material obtaining; • - equal degree of students involvement in the educational process; • - possibility for a teacher to renew and add information or activities; • - possibility for students to material processing several times; • - spoken and written interaction with students.
Disadvantages	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - class time limitation; - impossibility to cover of the entire group for interaction. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - necessity of good self-education skills and self-discipline for doing tasks; - absence of live contact; - impossibility to ask questions if he/she needs; - prevailing written interaction and written form of assessment.

As it was shown in the table that the main benefits of offline opportunities are possibility to create live communication, immediate feedback and personal interaction which led to effective communication and obtaining new experience. In spite of possibility for creation both asynchronous and synchronous virtual environments the written communication prevails over oral in online format. So, instructional strategies in online approach are presented in the written forms that lead to some difficulties for students in information processing and doing activities. It is known that each student has individual cognitive style, that ignores in online approach, because the teachers see only the product (results) of the independent study activities they can't possibility to manage student's procedural aspect in material obtaining. At the same time both offline and online pedagogical discourse organization require to establish a supportive learning environment, encourage active participation, and foster meaningful interactions among students through clear instructional strategies.

By understanding the unique characteristics in obtaining the interactional strategies such as information sharing and engaging learners into educational process in both format (offline and online), it is necessary to conduct a survey. Survey was organized among the 4-th year students in the faculty of foreign language of TSPU in October 2023. The goal of survey was to reveal students' attitude to offline and online forms of

teaching in mastering pedagogical discourse within the topic "Teacher's talk". The material for this topic was designed for offline and online classes. The questionnaire method was used in this survey. Questionnaire included 5 questions:

1. Do you prefer online or offline forms of learning material?
2. Are the activities the same for offline and online lessons or not?
3. Which activities are more successful for you?
4. Could you master the interactional skills which are necessary to teachers in online format?
5. Would you like to combine offline and online approaches in mastering teacher's talk patterns?

According to student's answers 5 questions, it was found out that

1. 60 % of student prefer the online approach then offline (40%) because they have more time for materials obtaining.
2. More than 76 % consider that the activities for offline and online lessons are the same but some activities for online differ and are difficult for doing (24 %)
3. All students point out the mind-mapping, answer-question, true and false, mini-teaching, problem-solving and analytical activities as successful for them.
4. 71 % are sure that the interactional skills can be developed better within the offline format, and 29%

points out that online instructions help development of language and reflective skills successfully.

5. 86% of students express that it is rational to combine offline and online approaches to mastering teacher's talk patterns, because of the specificity of the spoken interaction. However, 14 % express their disagreement.

At the same time, in students view both forms of education approximately equal in their effectiveness. We are sure that incorporation of traditional approach (offline) with online elements allows to making the educational process more effective and intensive. The teacher needs to include online activities for reading some lecture material, or watch video-lesson and in the class the teacher has a lot of opportunities to practice the pedagogical strategies, or allow students to organizing mini teaching activity. The successful methods for implementation into online format are case study and projects. In the case the student themselves solve problems according to the given instructions and in the project, they search information, then process it and write presentation for discussion of the main points in the class.

Conclusion. In conclusion, the practice of teaching pedagogical discourse encompass both offline and online formats. While offline teaching promotes immediate feedback and social interactions, online teaching offers flexibility and inclusive learning opportunities. Educators should consider the unique characteristics of each format when designing instructional input and fostering meaningful pedagogical discourse. By leveraging the power of each format, teachers can create meaningful learning experiences that meet the diverse needs of students in offline and online environments.

Limitation of the study is seen in detail description of the offline and online materials to see their peculiarities. Online learning has become a significant advantage in the higher education system, in particular in English. In the educational process, this format continues to be successfully used during practical and interactive classes, consultations, conferences, competitions and in other situations when full-time participation of students is problematic. We can conclude that online learning requires highly developed self-training skills. The level of students' proficiency in digital skills is also of great importance. These two factors are crucial for the successful completion of the online course. In turn, the offline mode has serious limitations in terms of location and time of events. Practice has shown that it is the hybrid format that allows you to overcome these barriers by using the advantages of the online format and direct contact between students and the teacher. That is, despite the new opportunities for teaching online, we are not going to abandon the traditional classroom methods of working in an academic environment with its live communication between teachers and students.

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